

On The Quinary Homogeneous Cubic Polynomial Diophantine Equation

$$x^3 + y^3 + (x + y)(x - y)^2 = 23(z + w) P^2$$

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Abstract

The homogeneous cubic Diophantine equation with five unknowns represented by $x^3 + y^3 + (x + y)(x - y)^2 = 23(z + w)P^2$ is analyzed for its patterns of non – zero distinct integral solutions.

Keywords: Cubic Equation, Homogeneous cubic equation, Quinary cubic equation, Integral Solutions.

Introduction

The subject of Diophantine equations is a treasure house in which the search for many hidden connections is a treasure hunt. In other words, the theory of Diophantine equations is an ancient subject that typically involves solving, polynomial equation in two or more variables or a system of polynomial equations with the number of unknowns greater than the number of equations, in integers. It is worth to observe that cubic Diophantine equations fall into the theory of Elliptic curves which are used in Cryptography. Many third degree Diophantine equations in two or three variables can be represented as elliptic curves that are used to generate public and private key pairs. Cubic Diophantine equations such as $x^3 + y^3 = z^3 + w^3$ requiring integer solutions form the backbone of many advanced mathematical and computational fields. Researchers utilize cubic equation with four variables

such as $x^3 + y^3 = 2nzw^2$ to produce sequences of figurate numbers. For simplicity and brevity, refer [1-23] for various problems on the cubic diophantine equations. However, often we come across homogeneous and non-homogeneous cubic equations and as such one may require its integral solution in its most general form. Here, the problem of obtaining solutions in integers to the third degree polynomial equation having five unknowns given by $x^3 + y^3 + (x + y)(x - y)^2 = 23(z + w)P^2$ is studied.

Method of analysis

The homogeneous cubic polynomial diophantine equation with five unknowns to be solved for its non-zero distinct integral solutions is given by

$$x^3 + y^3 + (x + y)(x - y)^2 = 23(z + w)P^2 \tag{1}$$

Introducing the linear transformations

$$x = u + v, y = u - v, z = u + 1, w = u - 1, u \neq \pm 1, v \tag{2}$$

in (1), leads to

$$u^2 + 7v^2 = 23P^2 \tag{3}$$

To start with, by inspection, observe that (3) is satisfied by

$$u = 4 * 23\alpha, v = 23\alpha, P = 23\alpha$$

In view of (2), the values of x, y, z and w satisfying (1) are given by

$$x = 5 * 23\alpha, y = 3 * 23\alpha, z = 4 * 23\alpha + 1, w = 4 * 23\alpha - 1$$

Now, we present below different methods of solving (3) and thus obtain different Patterns of integral solutions to (1).

Pattern 1

Write (3) as

$$23P^2 - u^2 = 7v^2 \tag{4}$$

Assume

$$v = 23a^2 - b^2 \tag{5}$$

Consider the integer 7 on the R.H.S. of (4) to be

$$7 = (\sqrt{23} + 4)(\sqrt{23} - 4) \tag{6}$$

Substitute (5) & (6) in (4). Employing factorization and equating the positive factors, one has

$$\sqrt{23}P + u = (\sqrt{23} + 4)(\sqrt{23}a + b)^2$$

On equating the rational and irrational parts, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} u &= 4(23a^2 + b^2) + 46ab \\ P &= (23a^2 + b^2) + 8ab \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Using the values of u, v from (7), (5) in (2), one gets

$$\begin{aligned}x &= 5 * 23a^2 + 3b^2 + 46ab \\y &= 3 * 23a^2 + 5b^2 + 46ab \\z &= 4(23a^2 + b^2) + 46ab + 1 \\w &= 4(23a^2 + b^2) + 46ab - 1\end{aligned}\tag{8}$$

Thus, the values of x, y, z, w and P given by (8) and (7) satisfy (1).

Pattern 2

Write (3) as

$$23P^2 - 7v^2 = u^2 * 1\tag{9}$$

Assume

$$u = 4(23a^2 - 7b^2)\tag{10}$$

Consider the integer 1 on the R.H.S. of (9) to be

$$1 = \frac{(\sqrt{23} + \sqrt{7})(\sqrt{23} - \sqrt{7})}{16}\tag{11}$$

Substitute (10) & (11) in (9). Employing factorization and equating the positive factors, one has

$$\begin{aligned}\sqrt{23}P + \sqrt{7}v &= (2\sqrt{23}a + 2\sqrt{7}b)^2 \frac{(\sqrt{23} + \sqrt{7})}{4} \\&= (\sqrt{23}a + \sqrt{7}b)^2 (\sqrt{23} + \sqrt{7})\end{aligned}$$

On equating the coefficients of corresponding terms in the above equation, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned}v &= (23a^2 + 7b^2) + 46ab \\P &= (23a^2 + 7b^2) + 14ab\end{aligned}\tag{12}$$

Using the values of u, v from (10), (12) in (2), one gets

$$\begin{aligned}x &= 5 * 23a^2 - 3 * 7b^2 + 46ab \\y &= 3 * 23a^2 - 5 * 7b^2 - 46ab \\z &= 4(23a^2 - 7b^2) + 1 \\w &= 4(23a^2 - 7b^2) - 1\end{aligned}\tag{13}$$

Thus, the values of x, y, z, w and P given by (13) and (12) satisfy (1).

Pattern 3

Write (3) as

$$u^2 = 23P^2 - 7v^2\tag{14}$$

Insertion of the transformations

$$P = X + 7T, v = X + 23T, u = 4U \tag{15}$$

in (14) leads to

$$X^2 = U^2 + 161T^2 \tag{16}$$

which is satisfied by

$$T = 2rs, U = 161r^2 - s^2, X = 161r^2 + s^2$$

From (15), one has

$$\begin{aligned} u &= 644r^2 - 4s^2, v = 161r^2 + s^2 + 46rs \\ P &= 161r^2 + s^2 + 14rs \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

From (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 805r^2 - 3s^2 + 46rs \\ y &= 483r^2 - 5s^2 - 46rs \\ z &= 644r^2 - 4s^2 + 1 \\ w &= 644r^2 - 4s^2 - 1 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Thus, the values of x, y, z, w and P given by (18) and (17) satisfy (1).

Note 1

It is worth to mention that, apart from (15), one may consider the transformation as

$$P = X - 7T, v = X - 23T, u = 4U$$

For this choice, we get

$$\begin{aligned} u &= 644r^2 - 4s^2, v = 161r^2 + s^2 - 46rs \\ P &= 161r^2 + s^2 - 14rs \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

The corresponding integer solutions to (1) are

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 805r^2 - 3s^2 - 46rs \\ y &= 483r^2 - 5s^2 + 46rs \\ z &= 644r^2 - 4s^2 + 1 \\ w &= 644r^2 - 4s^2 - 1 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

together with P given by (19).

Further, (16) is written as the system of double equations as below in Table-1:

Table-1 System of double equations

System	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
X + U	T ²	7T ²	23T ²	161T ²	23T	161T
X - U	161	23	7	1	7T	T

Solving each of the above system of double equations, one obtains the values of X,U and T. Substituting these values in (15) and (2), the required integer solutions to (1) are obtained. For simplicity & brevity, we present below the respective six sets of integer solutions to (1):

$$\text{Set 1: } \begin{aligned} x &= 10s^2 + 52s - 216, y = 6s^2 - 44s - 424, z = 8s^2 + 4s - 319 \\ w &= 8s^2 + 4s - 321, P = 2s^2 + 16s + 88 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Set 2: } \begin{aligned} x &= 70s^2 + 116s + 6, y = 42s^2 - 4s - 70, z = 56s^2 + 56s - 31 \\ w &= 56s^2 + 56s - 33, P = 14s^2 + 28s + 22 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Set 3: } \begin{aligned} x &= 230s^2 + 276s + 70, y = 138s^2 + 92s - 6, z = 184s^2 + 184s + 33 \\ w &= 184s^2 + 184s + 31, P = 46s^2 + 60s + 22 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Set 4: } \begin{aligned} x &= 1610s^2 + 1656s + 423, y = 966s^2 + 920s + 217, z = 1288s^2 + 1288s + 321 \\ w &= 1288s^2 + 1288s + 319, P = 322s^2 + 336s + 88 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Set 5: } x = 102T, y = 26T, z = 64T + 1, w = 64T - 1, P = 22T$$

$$\text{Set 6: } x = 424T, y = 216T, z = 320T + 1, w = 320T - 1, P = 88T$$

Pattern 4

Write (3) in the form of ratio as

$$\frac{u + 4P}{P + v} = \frac{7(P - v)}{u - 4P} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta > 0 \quad (21)$$

After some algebra, it is seen that (21) is satisfied by

$$\begin{aligned} u &= 4\alpha^2 - 28\beta^2 + 14\alpha\beta \\ v &= -\alpha^2 + 7\beta^2 + 8\alpha\beta \\ P &= \alpha^2 + 7\beta^2 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

From (2), observe that

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 3\alpha^2 - 21\beta^2 + 22\alpha\beta \\ y &= 5\alpha^2 - 35\beta^2 + 6\alpha\beta \\ z &= 4\alpha^2 - 28\beta^2 + 14\alpha\beta + 1 \\ w &= 4\alpha^2 - 28\beta^2 + 14\alpha\beta - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Thus, the values of x, y, z, w and P given by (23) and (22) satisfy (1).

Note 2

It is worth to mention that (3) may also be expressed in the following ratio forms:

$$\frac{u + 4P}{P - v} = \frac{7(P + v)}{u - 4P} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta > 0$$

$$\frac{u + 4P}{7(P - v)} = \frac{(P + v)}{u - 4P} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta > 0$$

$$\frac{u + 4P}{7(P + v)} = \frac{(P - v)}{u - 4P} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta > 0$$

Following the above procedure, one obtains three more patterns of integer solutions to (1).

Pattern 5

Write (3) as

$$u^2 + 7v^2 = 23P^2 * 1 \tag{24}$$

Assume

$$P = 4(a^2 + 7b^2) \tag{25}$$

Consider the integers 1, 23 on the R.H.S. of (24) as

$$1 = \frac{(3 + i\sqrt{7})(3 - i\sqrt{7})}{16} \tag{26}$$

$$23 = (4 + i\sqrt{7})(4 - i\sqrt{7})$$

Substitute (25) & (26) in (24). Employing factorization and equating the positive factors, one obtains

$$u + i\sqrt{7}v = (4 + i\sqrt{7})(2a + i2\sqrt{7}b)^2 \frac{(3 + i\sqrt{7})}{4}$$

$$= (5 + i7\sqrt{7})(a + i\sqrt{7}b)^2 \tag{27}$$

$$= (5 + i7\sqrt{7})[f(a, b) + i\sqrt{7}g(a, b)]$$

where

$$f(a, b) = a^2 - 7b^2, g(a, b) = 2ab$$

Equating the real and imaginary parts in (27), one has

$$u = 5f(a, b) - 49g(a, b)$$

$$v = 7f(a, b) + 5g(a, b)$$

From (2), we have

$$x = 12f(a, b) - 44g(a, b)$$

$$y = -2f(a, b) - 54g(a, b) \tag{28}$$

$$z = 5f(a, b) - 49g(a, b) + 1$$

$$w = 5f(a, b) - 49g(a, b) - 1$$

Thus, the values of x, y, z, w and P given by (28) and (25) satisfy (1).

Note 3

Apart from (26), The integer 1 on the R.H.S. of (24) may be considered as below:

$$1 = \frac{[7r^2 - s^2 + i\sqrt{7}(2rs)][7r^2 - s^2 - i\sqrt{7}(2rs)]}{(7r^2 + s^2)^2}$$

$$1 = \frac{[r^2 - 7s^2 + i\sqrt{7}(2rs)][r^2 - 7s^2 - i\sqrt{7}(2rs)]}{(r^2 + 7s^2)^2}$$

$$1 = \frac{[14s^2 - 14s + 3 + i\sqrt{7}(2s-1)][14s^2 - 14s + 3 - i\sqrt{7}(2s-1)]}{(14s^2 - 14s + 4)^2}$$

$$1 = \frac{[7s^2 - 1 + i\sqrt{7}(2s)][7s^2 - 1 - i\sqrt{7}(2s)]}{(7s^2 + 1)^2}$$

$$1 = \frac{[2s^2 - 2s - 3 + i\sqrt{7}(2s-1)][2s^2 - 2s - 3 - i\sqrt{7}(2s-1)]}{(2s^2 - 2s + 4)^2}$$

Following the above procedure, one obtains some more patterns of integer solutions to (1).

Conclusion

In this paper, an attempt has been made to obtain infinitely many integral solutions of a Cubic Diophantine equation in five unknowns. To conclude one may search for pattern of solutions to other forms of cubic equations with multiple variables.

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